

THE USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE PREPARATION OF A FUTURE PHILOLOGIST

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Abstract. *This article discusses the method of using information technology in the study of the language of the specialty of philology students. The base of this technology is based on the knowledge of ICT, as well as interactive methods. One of the most important tasks of informatization of education is the formation of an information culture of a specialist, the level of formation of which is determined by the ability to use modern information technologies in professional (educational) activities.*

Keywords: *information technology, professional activity, global network, Internet resources, multimedia.*

Introduction

Modern education, general and vocational, cannot be fully implemented without the use of information and communication technologies (ICT).

With the advent and wide spread of global networks with everything a set of information and communication tools they provide, teachers got the opportunity to correctly organize teaching foreign languages using their capabilities (E.G. Azimov, M.A. Bovtenko, E.S. Polat, O.I. Rudenko-Morgun and others.).

Based on the focus of the modern educational process on the development of the activity and independence of students, the development of information and communication technologies (ICT) has recently intensified significantly to solve these problems.

The current stage of technical development opens up great opportunities for improving the process of forming foreign language communicative competence. Information and communication technologies make it possible to achieve the compliance of the language training of students with the requirements of the modern global information space and society for a person with the necessary sociocultural competencies. The use of video resources contributes:

- expansion and deepening of knowledge, skills and abilities of foreign language communicative activity;
- increasing motivation and independence in learning;
- makes classes more dynamic, informative, corresponding to modern educational requirements.

Students receive audiovisual practice, which contributes to an easier and stronger assimilation of the material, allowing them to effectively use the acquired knowledge, adapt their behavior to behavior close to a native speaker, and also be able to correctly and tolerantly interpret cultural and historical realities.

Main part. Research Methodology

A wide range of Internet resources, multimedia educational programs, authentic audio and video materials combine various aspects of speech interaction and allow students to act as recipients of foreign language speech in various speech situations.

The purpose of using ICT in modern education is to provide the education sector with a methodology and practice for the development and optimal use of e-learning tools focused on the implementation of the psychological and pedagogical goals of training and education. The main purpose of using computer technology is to improve the quality of education.

Informatization of education actualizes the following processes:

1) improving the methodology and strategy for selecting the content, methods and organizational forms of training, education, corresponding to the tasks of developing the personality of a student in modern conditions of the information society of global, mass communication;

2) creation of methodological training systems focused on the development of the intellectual potential of the student, the formation of skills to independently acquire knowledge, carry out information and educational, experimental and research activities, various types of independent information activities;

3) improving the mechanisms for managing the education system based on the use of automated data banks of scientific and pedagogical information, information and methodological materials, as well as communication networks;

4) creation and use of computer testing, diagnostic methods for monitoring and evaluating the level of knowledge of trainees.

According to researchers, the most important tasks of informatization of foreign language education are:

- improving the quality of training specialists based on the use of modern information technologies in the educational process;
- application of active teaching methods, increasing the creative and intellectual components of educational activities;
- integration of various types of educational activities (educational, research, etc.);
- adaptation of information technologies of training to the individual characteristics of the student;
- development of new information technologies of education, which contribute to the activation of the cognitive activity of the student and increase the motivation to master the means and methods of informatics for effective use in future professional activities;
- ensuring continuity and succession in training;
- development of information technologies for distance learning;
- improvement of the software and methodological support of the educational process;
- introduction of information technologies of education in the process of special professional training of specialists of various profiles.

The use of ICT in the educational process allows:

- rationally use the time of the training session;
- visualize the learning process;
- increase the cognitive activity of students;
- enhance educational effects;
- to implement a differentiated approach to students with different levels of readiness for learning;
- quickly and efficiently replicate didactic manuals, handouts;

- search and use of information from the Internet for practical exercises, design and research work;
- create tasks to check and control the assimilation of the material covered;
- improve the quality of mastering the educational process;
- maintaining an electronic journal, e-mail, compiling reports, schedules, teacher documentation and holding parent meetings, for extracurricular activities, participation in competitions, quizzes, olympiads of various levels, developing games in subjects;
- promptly exchange work experience and methodological materials with colleagues.

Gritsenko E.S., Shamov A.N. in his work, he proposes the following scheme, which reflects the actions to implement the tasks set using Internet resources:

1. Determination by the student of the task assigned to him.
2. The study of the information space of a new subject area, which involves:
 - introductory study of articles, materials, abstracts on Internet portals;
 - adaptation of the material to the task.
3. Formulation of the problem, taking into account the studied information.
4. Search for all possible ways to achieve the goal (annotation, relevance assessment) [3]

Initially, e-learning was meant as learning with a computer, but new technologies have changed the situation, and the concept of e-learning has expanded significantly and is divided into two groups: synchronous and asynchronous.

Synchronous e-education is learning that takes place between the teacher and the student online, but at a great distance. Training can take place individually or in groups, such as webinars. To organize such training, you need special software.

Asynchronous e-education is training in which the student receives all the material for self-study from an Internet resource or electronic media such as CDs, DVDs or flash cards. The student decides when and how to study, examples of such training are CD-courses, e-learning courses, distance learning, etc.

The set of significant advantages of using a computer in teaching over traditional classes include the following:

1. Information technologies significantly expand the possibilities of presenting educational information. The use of color, graphics, sound, all modern video equipment allows you to recreate the real environment of the activity.
2. The computer can significantly increase students' motivation for learning. Motivation is increased by applying adequate rewards for correct problem solving.
3. ICT involve students in the learning process, contributing to the widest disclosure of their abilities, enhancing mental activity.
4. The use of ICT in the educational process increases the possibility of setting educational tasks and managing the process of their solution. Computers allow you to build and analyze models of various objects, situations, phenomena.
5. ICTs make it possible to qualitatively change the control of students' activities, while providing flexibility in the management of the educational process.
6. The computer contributes to the formation of reflection in students. The training program enables students to visualize the result of their actions, determine the stage in solving the problem at which the error was made, and correct it.

The diverse possibilities of the Internet can and should find their application in modern education, in particular, in teaching Russian as a foreign language.

Recently, the possibilities of the Internet as a means of electronic communication have been actively used in the educational process. The use of electronic communication as a learning tool helps to partially solve one of the main tasks of learning - the creation of a natural language environment, since it provides additional opportunities for communication in the target language. The natural communication environment based on such means of electronic communication as e-mail, chat communication, forums, guest books, online diaries, can be used by Russian as a foreign language teachers to maintain and improve the level of knowledge, assess students' speech behavior in different communicative situations. At the same time, depending on the content and objectives of training, electronic communication can be carried out both in synchronous and asynchronous modes using various formats: text (e-mail, chat, forum, online diaries), audio or video (video conferencing, voicemail, forwarding of sound and video files).

The widespread use of information and communication technologies in the educational process of universities makes it possible to provide:

- variability and personal orientation of the educational process (designing individual educational trajectories);
- practical orientation of the educational process with the introduction of interactive activity components (mastering design-research and communication methods);
- completion of profile self-determination and formation of abilities and competencies necessary for continuing education in the relevant professional direction.

Recently, multimedia technologies have been actively developing - this is a special type of computer technology that combines both traditional static visual information (text, graphics) and dynamic information (speech, music, video clips, animation, etc.).

Multimedia is a joint representation of text, graphic, numerical, sound and video information. The graphical representation of the educational material allows students to focus on the key points of the topic being studied, enables the teacher to increase their motivation and increase their interest in learning and memorizing new material, i.e. to implement the fundamental didactic principle of teaching - the principle of visibility.

Conclusion

The e-learning system accelerates the process of forming linguistic and communicative competence at different levels. In classes using ICT, the following conditions should be used:

- taking into account the level of language proficiency of the training group - language portfolio,

- the principle of concentricism, dividing training into training blocks and using a demonstrative form and working with the following types of exercises:

- 1) representative;
- 2) imitative;
- 3) wildcard.

From a methodological point of view, ICT makes it possible to implement formative assessment, when assessment is carried out in the process of completing a task by a student in order to stimulate self-control and self-correction, as well as contribute to better assimilation of the material. The possibility of organizing mutual evaluation of each other's work by students is very important, for example, when teaching writing and speech skills. [7].

Thus, the concentration of modern technical teaching aids contributes to the modernization of the educational process, activates the mental activity of students, promotes the development of creativity of teachers, allows distance learning, develops a system of continuous education, thereby increasing the efficiency of the educational process. [2].

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